

ASYMPTOTIC APPROACH TO MICROMECHANICS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: The approximate analytic approach is elaborated to use efficiently the elasticity theory of anisotropic bodies and fracture mechanics for description of the behavior of composite materials in different loading conditions. The approach is based on asymptotic analysis of equilibrium or motion equations and boundary conditions for strongly anisotropic media using small parameters which characterize typical relationship between different rigidities. Such an analysis allows to formulate substantiated boundary problems of composite micromechanics admitting an analytical solution in many important cases. As result the stress distributions in fibers and matrix are calculated for static loading. The essential attention is paid to the fracture mechanics of composite material taking into account its inhomogeneous structure, particularly to adhesion fracture. The applicability of different conventional approaches to micromechanics of composite materials is examined,

KEYWORDS: composite structure, adhesion, fracture mechanics, stress distribution.

One of the basic properties of a composite material is its adhesive strength. The experimental study of this property (in case of a fibrous structure) can be based on measuring of a load corresponding to pulling of a fiber from matrix.

For correct calculation of adhesive strength using results of such experiment it is necessary, however, to solve a complicated mechanical problem about distribution of contact stresses between the fiber and matrix. The application of rigorous methods of the analysis of composites at a level of their components does not allow to obtain the exact analytical solution of the corresponding problem of the theory of elasticity. The engineering approach [1] therefore is widely used, in which it is supposed that the fibers work only on a tension, and matrix — on shear. Obviously, such an approach can not take into account a possible singularity of contact stresses at free boundary. Besides, at use of the simplified model there is a natural problem concerning the limits of applicability of its solutions even outside of stress concentrators .

The detailed representation about the stress state can be obtained by a finite element method. However for efficient application of numerical methods the preliminary analytical solutions correctly reflecting basic features of a stress distribution in a composite are also important.. In this paper the limits of applicability of mentioned discrete model of composite are firstly estimated and the representations for contact stresses , valid everywhere, except for a neighbourhood of singular points are obtained. These representations together with the singular solutions, constructed at the second stage, give the approximate solution of a problem uniformly suitable in all contact region.

1. For determination of applicability limits of discrete model of a composite material we consider a plane problem about pulling of a fiber from matrix having the shape of a half-strip ($0 \leq x < \infty$, $-b \leq y \leq b$), the sides ($y = \pm b$) of which are clumped. The fiber treated as an one-dimensional elastic rod is located in middle of a half-strip and coincides with an axis Ox . The contact on a line is accepted. The matrix, generally speaking, is considered as orthotropic one, the principal directions of elasticity coincide with Cartesian axes of coordinates x, y .

In such statement the problem is reduced to integration of equilibrium equations of a matrix

$$B_1 u_{xx} + G u_{yy} + (v_2 B_1 + G) v_{xy} = 0,$$

$$G v_{xx} + B_2 v_{yy} + (v_1 B_2 + G) u_{xy} = 0$$

at following boundary conditions:

$$\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{12} = 0 \quad (x = 0), u = U, v = 0 \quad (y = 0), u = v = 0 \quad (y = \pm b).$$

At infinity all functions are converted in zero. Here u, v - are components of a vector of displacements of a matrix; B_1, B_2 - stiffnesses of a matrix at tension and compression in two directions, G - stiffness at shear; σ_{11}, σ_{12} - axial and tangential stresses in a matrix; v_1, v_2 - coefficients of Poisson; x, y indices designate differentiation respect to corresponding coordinates.

The displacement $U(x)$ of a fiber satisfies the equation

$$EFU_{xx} = P_0 \delta(x) - 2\tau(x), \quad (1.1)$$

where EF - stiffness of a fiber at a tension; $\delta(x)$ - function of Dirac, P_0 - load applied to a fiber at a boundary point $x = 0$; $\tau(x)$ - contact stress between the fiber and matrix. As $v = 0$ ($v_x = 0$) at $y = 0$,

$$\tau(x) = Gu_y \Big|_{y=0}. \quad (1.2)$$

For study of the problem, which can not be solved exactly, we apply an asymptotic method [2]. As the contact stress (1.2) is determined only through function u and, according with decomposition of stress-strain state of the matrix [2,3] the solution is reduced (in a first approximation) to integration of the equation (1.1) with the account (1.2) and approximate equilibrium equations of a matrix

$$\omega^2 u_{xx} + u_{yy} = 0 \quad (\omega^2 = B_1/G), \quad (1.3)$$

with corresponding boundary conditions

$$u_x = 0 \quad (x = 0), Gu_y = \tau(x) \quad (y = 0), u = 0 \quad (y = \pm b). \quad (1.4)$$

At infinity all functions are converted in zero.

Applying Fourier cos-transformation on coordinate x to the equation (1.3), solving the obtained ordinary differential equation with account of transformed equalities (1.1), (1.2), (1.4) and performing the inverse transformation we obtain

$$u(x, y) = -\frac{2P_0}{\pi EF} \int_0^\infty \frac{ch(wys) - cth(wbs) sh(wys)}{s[s + g cth(wbs)]} \cos xs \, ds, \quad (1.5)$$

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos xs}{s th(wbs) + g} \, ds, \quad g = \frac{2G\omega}{EF}.$$

At small s , that corresponds to large values of coordinate x , $th(ws) \approx ws$, and the stress takes a form

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g_*^2}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos xs}{s^2 + g_*^2} ds = \frac{P_0 g_*}{2} e^{-g_* x}, \quad g_*^2 = \frac{g}{\omega b} = \frac{2G}{EFb}. \quad (1.6)$$

The contact stress (1.6) corresponds to the solution of a problem in the supposition that the matrix works only on shear.

At large s , that corresponds to small values of coordinate x , $th(ws) \approx 1$ and stress $\tau(x)$ from (1.5) will be written as

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos xs}{s + g} ds = -\frac{P_0 g}{\pi} (\cos gx \operatorname{ci} gx + \sin gx \operatorname{si} gx), \quad (1.7)$$

where $\operatorname{si}, \operatorname{ci}$ - integral sine and cosine. The distribution of contact stresses determined by the formula (1.7) corresponds to the solution of a pulling problem for a fiber and a semi-infinite matrix and $\tau(x)$ has, obviously, logarithmic singularity in a point $x = 0$.

Thus, solution obtained on the basis of the simplified analysis, when it is supposed, that the fibers work only on a tension, and the matrix on shear, is valid only at rather large values of coordinate x .

The similar results can be received for a problem about pulling of a fiber located along axis x from a matrix clumped at edges $y = \pm b$ and having the shape of a rectangle ($0 \leq x \leq h$, $-b \leq y \leq b$), when $\sigma_{11} = \sigma_{12} = 0$ at $x = 0, h$. In particular, the contact stress between the fiber and matrix is determined by the formula

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(n\pi x h^{-1})}{n \operatorname{th}(\omega n \pi b h^{-1}) + g h \pi^{-1}}. \quad (1.8)$$

If the matrix works only on shear

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g_*}{2} \frac{ch[g_*(h-x)]}{sh(g_* h)}. \quad (1.9)$$

At $h \rightarrow \infty$ the solution (1.8), (1.9) transfers in (1.5), (1.6).

In the previous examples it was supposed that fibers, nearest to pulling one, are anchored. The influence of these fibers, as it is shown above, is essential only at rather large values of coordinate x , where the solution obtained on the basis of the simplified analysis is valid. Therefore an actual structure of a composite can be taken into account rather simply. The corresponding calculations show, that the approach of anchored neighbour fibrils is quite acceptable.

The range of values of parameter s (and coordinate x) in which the discrete model of a composite is applicable may be estimated as follows: $s \leq g_*$ ($x \geq g_*^{-1}$).

In a region close to the edge of a strip ($x < g_*^{-1}$), the discrete model of composite material is inapplicable. Here it is necessary to use the solutions (1.5), (1.8), obtained by asymptotic method and valid everywhere, except an immediate neighbourhood of a joint of fiber and matrix on free boundary. In this neighbourhood the special solution should be constructed within the framework of the exact equations of the theory of elasticity. If in considered neighbourhood the stress state of fiber is described by the equations of the plane stress state, the singularity of contact stresses (not depending on the cross size of a fiber) is determined by an type of transfer of a load on fiber (the stresses or displacements are given). At given stresses the eigenvalue λ , determining an ex-

ponent of power singularity of contact stresses ($\tau(x) = Ax^\lambda$) in a neighbourhood of joint of fiber and matrix at free boundary, is a root of a characteristic equation

$$D_2^2 (1 + \lambda)^4 + (2D_1D_2 - 4D_1^2 - D_2^2 + 6D_1D_2 \cos \lambda\pi)(1 + \lambda)^2 + D_1^2(1 + \cos \lambda\pi)^2 + D_3^2 \sin^2 \lambda\pi = 0, \quad (1.10)$$

which is obtained as a result of the use of the group-theoretic approach [4]. Here $D_1 = k(\chi_2 - 1) - (\chi_1 - 1)$; $D_2 = 4(1 - k)$; $D_3 = k(\chi_2 + 1) - (\chi_1 + 1)$; $k = G_1/G_2$; $\chi_i = (3 - \nu_i)/(3 + \nu_i)$; coefficients 1 and 2 concern to fiber and matrix.

The solutions of the equation (1.10) locating at region $-1 < \lambda < 0$, incidentally depend on the change of parameters and are in an interval $-0.419 \leq \lambda \leq -0.394$ (at $\nu_1 = \nu_2 = 0.3 \lambda = -0.412$).

2. We consider now similar axysymmetric problem. Let a fiber of circular cross section is pulled out from a matrix having the shape of the semi-infinite cylinder ($a \leq r \leq b, 0 \leq z < \infty$), which boundary ($r = b$) is anchored. The medial line of a fiber is perpendicular to plane $z = 0$ and coincides with axis Oz . It is required to find the distribution law of contact stresses between the fiber and matrix when in the end section ($z = 0$) of fiber an axial load with equal in effect value P_0 , directed on the axis of the fiber.

At statement of spatial contact problems for bodies with elastic inclusions of small cross section the model of an one-dimensional elastic rod in a combination with the model of contact on a line is immediately inapplicable. Therefore, maintaining for a fiber the model of an elastic rod, we accept its contact to a matrix on a cylindrical surface.

In such statement and according to decomposition of a stress-strain state of a matrix [2] the solution (in the first approach) is reduced to integration of the equation for a fiber

$$d^2 \omega_1 / dz^2 = (P_0 \delta(z) - \tau(z)) / EF \quad (2.1)$$

and approximate equilibrium equation of a matrix,

$$\partial^2 \omega / \partial r^2 + (1/r) \partial \omega / \partial r + \omega^2 \partial^2 \omega / \partial z^2 = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\omega_z = 0 \quad (z = 0), \omega = \omega_1 \quad (r = a), \omega = 0 \quad (r = b), \quad (2.3)$$

on infinity all functions are converted in zero. Here E, F - elastic modulus of a material and cross-sectional area of the fiber; $\omega(\omega_1)$ - normal (along axis z) displacements of matrix (fiber); $\tau(z) = 2\pi a G \omega_r|_{r=a}$ - contact stress on unity of length of the fiber, which has to be found.

After application of Fourier cos-transformation on coordinate z to the equations and boundary conditions, solution of the ordinary differential equation obtained from (2.2), and evaluation of pre-images leads to expressions

$$\tau(x) = \frac{2P_0 g_1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos zs}{s f(s) + g_1} ds, \quad (2.4)$$

where $g_1 = \frac{2\pi a G \omega}{EF} = \frac{2G\omega}{Ea}$; $f(s) = \frac{I_0(wbs)K_0(was) - I_0(was)K_0(wbs)}{I_0(wbs)K_0(was) + I_0(was)K_0(wbs)}$;

$I_k(x), K_k(x)$ ($k = 0, 1$) - modified Bessel functions.

At large values of parameter s , that correspond to small values of coordinate z , $f(s) \approx 1$, and the contact stress is expressed as follows:

$$\tau(x) = \frac{2P_0 g_1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos zs}{s + g_1} ds = -\frac{2P_0 g_1}{\pi} (\cos g_1 z ci g_1 x + \sin g_1 z si g_1 x). \quad (2.5)$$

The distribution of contact stresses (2.5) corresponds to the solution of a pulling problem for a fiber and semi-infinite matrix; as well as in a plane problem, we have logarithmic singularity at $z = 0$.

At small s , that correspond to large values of coordinate z ,

$$f(s) \approx [1 + \chi(s)]^{-1} \omega \alpha s \ln(b/a), \quad \chi(s) = \left((\omega \alpha s)^2 / 2 \right) \ln(2/\gamma \omega b s),$$

γ - is the Euler constant. At small s it is possible to neglect by function $\chi(s)$ in comparison with unity, then $f(s) \approx \omega \alpha s \ln(b/a)$.

In this case the stress (2.4) has a form

$$\tau(x) = -\frac{P_0 g_{1*}^2}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos zs}{s^2 + g_{1*}^2} ds = \frac{P_0 g_{1*}}{2} e^{-g_{1*} z}, \quad g_{1*}^2 = \frac{g_1}{\omega \alpha \ln(b/a)} = \frac{2G}{Ea^2 \ln(b/a)}. \quad (2.6)$$

The formulas (1.6), (2.6) are identical, however last one does not correspond to distribution of contact stresses a discrete composite model.

Thus, in a spatial problem the solution obtained on the basis of the simplified approach, when it is supposed that the fibers work only on a tension and matrix — on shear, does not correspond to an asymptotics of the exact solution. Therefore it is possible to consider such simplified approach as justified one only in a plane problem, and the field of its applicability is restricted.

The similar results are obtained for rotationally symmetric problem about pulling of a fiber from matrix having the shape of the finite cylinder ($a \leq r \leq b, 0 \leq z < h$), which lateral area ($r = b$) is anchored.

As well as in a plane problem the singular behaviour of contact stresses in a neighbourhood of the singular line $r = a, z = 0$ is found on the basis of the complete equations of the theory of elasticity. As this takes place, the eigenvalues λ of singular solution turn out to be the same in plane t and spatial problems, if the boundary conditions at the end of fiber are identical.

3. The solutions for contact stresses obtained above which are valid in the different regions of contact surface, should smoothly transfer one in another. The connection between the solutions in two neighbour regions can be set as follows. In one of the regions the solution is known completely. In the solution for the neighbour region a coefficient is unknown. The requirement of coincidence of the solutions and their derivatives allows to find the unknown coefficient and coordinate of a point of matching of these two solutions.

Let us perform, for example, the matching of the solution (1.8), which includes the solutions (1.7), (1.9), with the singular solution in a neighbourhood of the joint of the fiber and matrix at free boundary ($x = 0$), when the stress state of a fiber in a given vicinity is described by the equations of the plane stress state. In this case

$$\tau_1(\xi) = A \xi^\lambda, \quad \tau_2(\xi) = (2P_0/\pi b) g_2 \varphi(\xi),$$

$$\text{where } \varphi(\xi) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(n\pi\beta^{-1}\xi)}{n \operatorname{th}(2n\pi\beta^{-1}) + 2g_2\beta\pi^{-1}}; \quad \xi = \frac{x}{b}; \quad \beta = \frac{h}{b}; \quad g_2 = \frac{2GB}{EF}; \quad \omega = 2.$$

Requiring the conditions $\tau_1 = \tau_2, \quad \tau_1' = \tau_2'$, we obtain

$$A_1 = \frac{2P_0}{\pi b} A_1^*, \quad A_1^* = g_2 \xi_*^{-\lambda} \varphi(\xi_*).$$

Here ξ_* (the point of matching of the solutions) is a root of the equation

$$\lambda\varphi(\xi) - \xi\varphi'(\xi) = 0.$$

In particular, at $\lambda = -0.4$, $\beta = 1$ for values $g_2 = 0.01; 0.1; 0.3; 0.5; 0.8; 1.0$ we found accordingly the following values ξ_* and A_1^* : $\xi_* = 0.026; 0.024; 0.02; 0.019; 0.017; 0.015$; $A_1^* = 0.006; 0.056; 0.157; 0.248; 0.368; 0.441$. At $\beta = 2$ and same values of λ and g_2 we have $\xi_* = 0.053; 0.045; 0.037; 0.029; 0.022; 0.021$; $A_1^* = 0.008; 0.072; 0.191; 0.291; 0.418; 0.493$.

Matching of the solutions can be similarly performed in the case of rotationally symmetric problem.

REFERENCES

1. Michailov A.M. "Fracture of unidirectional composite", *Solid State Mechanics*, №5, Moscow, Nauka, 1973.
2. Manevitch L.I., Pavlenko A.V. "Asymptotic method in micromechanics of composites", Kiev, Vyshcha Shkola, 1991.
3. Manevitch L.I., Pavlenko A.V. "Transfer of a longitudinal load from a rod to orthotropic strip", *Solid State Mechanics*, №2, Moscow, Nauka, 1975.
4. Cherepanov G.N. "Mechanics of brittle fracture". Moscow, Nauka, 1974.